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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“UNTIL THE SUMMIT”

He started a journey—
Having nothing but flames

He walked—
on roads only few could bear
each step, a test of courage
facing the thorn—a hurdle

He continued—
Even climbed the mountain top
Without fanfare or flags—
He didn't stop

He stepped—
Into the darkest forest
Burning every doubts and made it his light

He faced—
the tallest tree in front of him

He stopped—
as he carved his name on the tree

He succeeded—
Now a doctor's crown, rest on his weary name
A title forged from undying flames